

Speculation on Gauss' Law Following from Special Relativity and the Nature of a Delta Function

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. March 14, 2024

Gauss' Law: $\text{grad dot } E = 1/(4 \cdot 3.14 \cdot \epsilon_0)$ charge density, is one of Maxwell's EM laws and is experimentally verifiable.

In this note, we speculate that Gauss' Law may follow from special relativity and the nature of a delta function. We suggest that E for a spherical point charge should drop as some $1/R$ (power) or a sum of such terms with different powers. This means that it is singular at the origin. From Newtonian mechanics: $E = -\text{grad } \phi$, so ϕ should also be singular. We note that this singularity only occurs if one has a point charge and so should be associated with the some singular math function linked to a point charge. The density $= q \delta(r)$ is such a function. We argue that formally a delta function is 0 every except at $r=0$, but we suggest that coarse graining exists and that tiny spheres (constant surface charge density) with the same charge Q give rise to the same E field. In other words, this means that a point charge is equivalent to a number of concentric spheres with constant charge density such that they have the same charge. This suggests that the essential information is the total charge.

We seek to connect ϕ to a Lorentz invariant operator which might connect it to a delta function. From special relativity: $E = -\text{grad } \phi - dA/dt$ partial. Using the Lorentz gauge (continuity equation for energy-momentum) and $\text{Grad dot } E$ on has: D' Alembertian $\phi =$ function(r). Function of r is unknown, but must transform as the fourth component of a four-vector.'

Thus, ϕ is somehow connected to a delta-function singularity and different tiny spheres yield the same E field. One could in principle seek a function $g(D';\text{Alembertian})$ such that $g()$ $\phi =$ delta function, but we suggest that $\text{grad dot } E$ has geometrical flow significance. In particular, $\text{Integral grad dot } E \text{ volume} = E(r) 4 \cdot 3.14 r r$. Given that different spheres have the same charge and yield the same E , we argue that charge is the only information in the situation and that $E(r) 4 \cdot 3.14 r r$ should be proportional to charge and not contain r . Given that one takes the volume integral of $\text{grad dot } E$, one should take the volume integral of charge density. This suggests that in the rest frame, it is $\text{grad dot grad } \phi = -1/(4 \cdot 3.14 \cdot \epsilon_0) q \delta$ function, which it is for $\phi=C1/r$.

Electric Field, Electrostatic Potential and R Dependence

A charged particle creates a force on a test charge q depending on how far away the test charge is. If it is at infinite, it does not feel a force. Thus, we argue that:

$$E = \text{Sum over } n \ 1/ R^{\text{power } n} \text{ where } n \text{ can be any positive number} > 0 \quad ((1))$$

We also suggest that $\text{Force} = qE = -q \text{ grad } \phi$ from Newtonian mechanics. ((2))

We also suggest that Force is proportional to Q . ((3))

Given that one deals with total charge, one does not use charge density in ((2)) or ((3)). In other words, a point charge is the same as a small spherical shell of charge with a constant surface charge density such that the total charge is Q. Otherwise one would need a different force equation than ((2)).

We suggest that this same idea is found in the notion of point charge which is described by a delta function. The delta function describes a spherical point and may be approximated by various different tiny shells with constant charge density such that the total charge is Q. We suggest that experimentally one does not distinguish between these various tiny shells because in reality one does not physically have a point charge. We consider this a key point because it means that the essential pieces of information are spherical symmetry for both radius and charge density and the overall charge Q.

We note that both E and phi are singular if one has a point charge. We argue that somehow the exact singularity of the point charge (associated with a delta function charge density) must be equivalent to some function of phi, in particular one that uses derivatives seems reasonable. This function must be Lorentz invariant in order to have a theory which holds as seen from different frames moving with constant v.

The question becomes: Can one use special relativity to find a Lorentz invariant operator linked to phi?

We note that qphi is potential energy in a rest frame and so should transform as the fourth component of a 4-vector.

Thus: $(0, q\phi) \rightarrow (A', q\phi')$ where $q\phi' = g\phi$ and $A' = g v \phi$ ((4))

where $g = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$.

In the lab frame, $E = -\text{grad } \phi$, but if E is to depend on the vector $\{ (x''-vt''), y'', z'' \}$ in the moving frame, then $-\text{grad } \phi$ does not suffice because a Lorentz transformation changes an r vector i.e.

$y'' = y'', z'' = z'', x'' = \text{position in moving frame} = g(x''-vt'')$ ((5))

In other words, there is a problematic g factor. If phi is a function of $r'' = \sqrt{g^2((x''-vt'')^2 + y''^2 + z''^2)}$ then $d/dx'' \rightarrow gg$ while $d/dt'' \text{ partial} \rightarrow gg(-v)$. Given that $gg = 1/(1-vv/cc)$, the combination:

$-\text{grad}'' \phi'' - d/dt'' A'' \text{ partial}$ removes the gg because A is proportional to vphi.

Thus: $E'' = -\text{grad}'' \phi'' - dA''/dt'' \text{ partial}$.

If one considers: $\text{grad}'' \text{ dot } E'' = -\text{grad}'' \text{ dot grad}'' \phi'' - d/dt'' \text{ grad}'' \text{ dot } A'' \text{ partial}$ then one may

Use the Lorentz gauge $d\phi''/dt'' + \text{grad}'' \text{ dot } A'' = 0$. We argue that this is a continuity equation because $q\phi''$ is energy and A'' is momentum.

Then: $\text{grad} \cdot \text{E} = -\text{grad} \cdot \text{grad} \phi + \frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt} \phi$ ((6))

One thus has the Lorentz invariant D'Alembertian operator. We suggest that one should consider this operator or a general function of it acting on ϕ as the way of obtaining a delta function.

We now move back to the rest frame, where the operator in question is $-\text{grad} \cdot \text{grad}$ acting on ϕ . We note that $\text{grad} \cdot \text{E}$ has important flow implications and so consider it before seeking a general function of the D'Alembertian.

We argued above that different spherical shells with constant density such that the total charge is the same, i.e. Q , yield the same E . Thus, the information is Q , not r . An integral of $\text{grad} \cdot \text{E}$ over volume is:

$\int dv \text{grad} \cdot \text{E} = E \cdot 4\pi r^2$ because $E(r)$ is spherical ((7))

Given that information is only dependent on total charge Q , $E(r)$ should be proportional to $1/r$.

This means that ϕ is $1/r$. We now seek a function which acts on $1/r$ in order to create a delta function.

We check to see if $-\text{grad} \cdot \text{grad} \phi$ with $\phi = 1/r$ satisfies this condition. We see that it does.

$\{ r = \sqrt{xx+yy+zz} \quad \text{div} (\mathbf{x} / (rr)^{3/2}) = 3 / (rr)^{1.5} - x_i x_i 3 / (rr)^{5/2} = 0 \}$

$-\text{grad} \cdot \text{grad}$ is linked to the D'Alembertian so one has a Lorentz invariant operator. One also has the delta function in the moving frame.

Thus, we suggest that: $\text{grad} \cdot \text{E} = \text{constant charge density}$ ((8)) i.e. Gauss' Law.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we speculate that one may be able to derive Gauss' Law by suggesting that a delta function charge density implies that different tiny spherical shells with constant charge density and the same overall charge Q create the same spherical E field. We suggest that both E and $-\text{grad} \phi$ (in a rest frame) drop as powers of r and so are singular at $r=0$. We suggest that there exists a derivative function operator which acts on ϕ creates the delta function singularity because ϕ is only singular because one has a point charge. This operator must be Lorentz invariant.

We show that $E = -\text{grad} \phi - \frac{dA}{dt}$ partial in a moving frame and that this is equivalent to $\text{grad} \cdot \text{E} = \text{D'Alembertian} \phi$ using the Lorentz gauge. As a guess, we consider $\text{grad} \cdot \text{E}$ and $-\text{grad} \cdot \text{grad}$ acting on ϕ in a rest frame. The volume integral of $\text{grad} \cdot \text{E}$ yields $E(r) \cdot 4\pi r^2$. Given that different tiny spheres produce the same $E(r)$ field, we suggest that this integral

should only depend on Q and not on r . This leads to $\phi = C1/r$ and the special operator $-\text{grad dot grad}$ in the rest frame. We check whether this operator acting on ϕ creates the delta function singularity and it does. This operator becomes the D'Alembertian in the moving frame, while the charge density is still a delta function. Thus, we suggest that one has Gauss' Law: $-\text{grad dot E} = 1/(4*3.14e_0)$ charge density which holds in both the rest and moving frame.s